

Kiraṇa, catuṣpañcāśat paṭalaḥ, edition

N f79v, line5; G2 f185r; G3 f88r; M1c p120; M2c p167; E p141.

garuḍa uvāca

54.1 prāsādānāṃ tu yat sthānaṃ tad bhūbhāgaparīkṣaṇam
saśalyā vā yadā brūhi viśalyā kriyate katham

bhagavān uvāca

54.2 mahendrādīnagesv eva cānyasmimṣ tīrthasaṃśraye
mahānadītaṭāyoge jñātvaivaṃ bhūparigraham

54.3 dvijādīkramāc ca snigdhāṃ rūpabhāravatīm dṛḍhāṃ
śūrpakūrmākṛtīm tyaktvā sā grāhyā sphuṭitā na yā

54.4 samāṃ kṛtvā tathākoṭya nyase 'pakvaṃ ghaṭaṃ śubham
vardhamānaṃ tadūrdhvaṃ syāt sthāpyaṃ vartīcatuṣṭayam

N f80r

G = G2, G3 (and G3c) M = M1c and M2c Ω = N G M

before 1a garuḍa uvāca] N; garuḍaḥ G,M,E

1a prāsādānāṃ tu yat] NG2,M,E; prāsā[– – –]t G3

1b tad] N,G3c,M,N; tat G • bhāga] N,G2; nāga G3; tāga M; tāṅga E

• parīkṣaṇam] N,M1c,G,E; parīkṣaṇam M2c 1c vā yadā] N,G3,M,E; [– – –] G2

1d viśalyā] G,M,E; viśalyaḥ N before 2a bhagavān uvāca] N; bhagavān G,M,E

2a mahendrādi] NG,E; mahendrodi M • nagesv] N,G,E; ragesv M

2ab eva cānyasmimṣ] E; evacānyasmin G; evānyasmin M1c; evavānyasmin M2c; evacānyevā N

2c taṭāyoge] G,M; taṭeyoge N; taṭābhoge E 2d jñātvaivaṃ] N,G3,M,E; jñātvevaṃ G2

• bhū] N,G; tri M; triḥ E • parigraham] M,G,E; gṛhamataḥ N 3a dvijādi] conj.; dvijāti N,G,M,E

• kramāc ca] N; prakramāt G,M,E • snigdhāṃ] N; siddhiṃ G2; siddhaṃ G3,M,E

3b bhāravatīm] G,E; bhāravatī N,M 3c śūrpa] N,G2,G3,E; śarapa M

• kūrmākṛtīm] conj. Sanderson; sūryākṛtīm G3,M,E; sūryākṛtīm G2; sūryākṛtī N

3d sā grāhyā] G,E; saṃgrāhyā N,M • yā] G,M,E; yāt N

4a samāṃ] N; samaṃ G,M,E • tathākoṭya] N; tathākoṭyā G,M,E

4b nyase] conj. Sanderson; niśi G,M,E; nisva N

• 'pakvaṃ ghaṭaṃ śubham] conj. Sanderson: pakṣeghaṭaśubhe NGM

4c ūrdhvaṃ] G,M,E; ūrdhvaḥ N 4d sthāpyaṃ] G2,M,E; sthāpya N,G3

• vartī] conj. Sanderson; nakti G,M2c; natti M1c; nakta E; bahi N

- 54.5 pūrvādīkramayogena dvijādīnām kramo bhavet
kalpyaṃ narādibhir mantrair abhimantrya śataṃ śatam
- 54.6 jñeyā hrāsavivṛddhyā sā saṃkīrṇā kevalāthavā
kṣītiṃ ca karṣītāṃ kṛtvā yavān vāpi tilān kiret M1c p121; M2c p168
- 54.7 yā bījakṣepaṇād bījatryahotthānāc chubhāvaniḥ
anyathā viphalā jñeyā yathā sevā kurājani
- 54.8 dine yogādisaṃyukte puṇyāhajayamaṅgalaiḥ
tataḥ prasārayet sūtram ācāryaḥ śilpibhiḥ saha G3 f88v
- 54.9 tasmin prasāryamāṇe tu nimittāny upalakṣayet
nimitte satī taṃ kuryād animitte kratuḥ bhavet
- 54.10 ghoreṇāṣṭasahasraṃ tu kāryo homaḥ sitais tilaiḥ
ghṛtakṣīrayutaiḥ śāntir bhavaty atra na saṃśayaḥ G2 f186r

G = G2, G3 (and G3c) M = M1c and M2c Ω = N G M

5b dvijādīnām] G,M; dvijātīnām E; dvijātīnā N

5c kalpyaṃ] G3,E; kalpya N; kalpye G2; kalpitā M1c; kalpinā M2c

• narādibhir] G3,E; narādibhiḥ N,G2; rādhibhir M1c; rādhir M2c

• mantrair] N,M2c,G3,E; maṃtraī[[h]]r G2; māntrair M1c 5d abhimantrya] M,G2,G3,E; jāpyacāṣṭa N

6a jñeyā] G,M,footnote to E; jñeyo N,E • vivṛddhyā] G2,G3,E,footnote to E; vivṛddhā M; vivṛddhās N

• sāl] footnote to E; sa G,M,E; tā N 6b saṃkīrṇā] N, footnote to E; saṅkīrṇaḥ E; saṃkīrṇo G,M

• kevalāthavā] N; kevalā 'thavā footnote to E; kevalothavā G,M; kevalo'thavā E

6c karṣītāṃ] G2,E; karṣitaṃ N,G3,M2c; karṣatiṃ M1c 6d yavān] G,M,E; yavā N • vāpi] N,G,M; vā'pi E

• tilān] G,M2c,E; tinaṅ N; kilān M1c 7a yā] E; yaṃ N,G,M

• kṣepaṇād] M,E; kṣepaṇāt G; kṣepatam N • bīja] N,M2c; bījā G2; bījās E; bījāt G3,M1c

7b tryahotthānāc] conj.; tryahotthānaṃ N; tryahotthānās G2; tryahoddhānāc G3,M1c; tryahoddānāc M2c;

trahobhissāṅkurās E

• chubāvaniḥ] em. Sanderson; chubhāvati G3,; śubhāvati G2; chubhāratī M; śubhāmatā N; śubhā E

7d sevā kurājani] N; sevākurājani G,M; 'smin sāṅkurasthale E

8a yogādisaṃyukte] N,G2,M,E; yogodisaṃyukto G3 8b puṇyāha] N,G; puṇyāhaṃ M, E

8d ācāryaḥ] M; ācāryās G,E; ācārya N • śilpibhiḥ] M1c; śilpibhis N,G,M2c,E

9a tasmin prasāryamāṇe tu] N; prasāryamāṇe sūtre tu E; prasāryamāṇenatusūtre G2; prasāryamāṇe[- -]

M; prasāryamāṇe[- -] G3

9b nimittāny] G,M,E; nimittān N 9c satī] N,G,E; satri M • taṃ] G2, taṃ N; kaṃ M; kiṅ E; kaḥ G3

• kuryād] M1c,E; kuryāt N,G; kuryā M2c 9d kratuḥ] G,M,E; kṛte N

10b kāryo homaḥ] M1c; kāryohomas G2,E; kāryohoma G3; kāryairhoma M2c; kāryājyenā N

10c yutaiḥ] M1c; yutaiś N,G3,M2c,E; yutai G2 • śāntir] N,G,E; śāntiḥ M;

10d bhavaty] N,G,E; phalaty M

- 54.11 caturaśraṃ samaṃ kṛtvā navadhā kārayet pari
īśādito bhaven nyāsas tatreśaḥ prathamo bhavet
- 54.12 parjanyo jayamāhendrau bhāskaraḥ satyabhṛt punaḥ
antarikṣaś ca pūrve syād dakṣiṇe śikhipūṣaṇau
- 54.13 vitatho gṛhakṣataś ca yamo gandharvabhṛṅgarāt
mṛgaś ca kathitā yāmye paścime piṭṣaṃjñakaḥ
- 54.14 dauvārikaś ca sugrīvaḥ puṣpadanto jalādhipaḥ
asuraḥ śoṣarogākhyau paścime kathitā mayā
- 54.15 uttare vāyunāgau ca mukhyabhallāṭasomakāḥ
ṛgyaditī ditiś ceti sthitāś cottaradiggatāḥ

M lacks verse 14 after *śoṣayā* in *pāda c*, and 15ab except for *mukhye*.

G = G2, G3 (and G3c) M = M1c and M2c Ω = N G M

- 11a aśraṃ] N,G2,E; aśra G3,M • samaṃ] G,M,E; pura N
11b pari] N,G3,M,E; padaṃ G2 11c īśādito] N; īśānādir G2,E; īśānādi G3,M
• bhaven] N,G2,E; praven M2c; prave G3,M1c 11d tatreśaḥ] G,M,E; tatresa N
12a parjanyo] N,E; parjanye G,M • māhendrau] em.; māhendro NGM
12b bhāskaraḥ] N,M1c; bhāskaras G2,M2c,E; bhāskara G3
• bhṛt punaḥ] N; bhraṃśakaḥ E; bhāgaśaḥ M; bhākaśaḥ G3; kābhaśaḥ G2
12c antarikṣaś] N; aṃtarikṣas E; antarikṣaṃ M,G • ca] N; tu G,M,E
• pūrve] N,E; pūrvaṃ G,M • syād] G3,E; syāt G2,M; tu N
12d pūṣaṇau] E; pūṣakau G,M; bhūṣakau N
13a vitatho] N,G2; tītatho G3; titathe M; dhātā E
• kṣataś] E; sāraś N,M2c; sāraś G3,M1c; śāra G2 • ca] N,G,M; caiva E
13c mṛgaś ca] N,G2; mṛgarāt E; vṛṣaśca G3,M • yāmye] N,G,E; hyete M
13d piṭṣaṃjñakaḥ] N; piṭṣaṃkhyayā G2; pretasaṃvahaḥ E; vṛttasaṃkhyayā G3,M
14a dauvārikaś] G,M,E; dvauvārikas N • sugrīvaḥ] E; sugrīva N; sugrīve G,M
14b danto] N,E; dante M,G 14c asuraḥ] N,M1c; asuraś G,M2c,E
• rogākhyau] E; rogākhye G2, pāyākhyā N; yāvākhye G3; yā[– –] M
14d kathitā] N,G; kathitau E 15a vāyu] G2,E; roga N,G3
• nāgau] G2,E; nāsas N; nābha G3 15b mukhya] G,E; mukhyo N • somakāḥ] E;
saumyagaḥ N; saumyagau G 15c ṛgyaditī ditiś] em.; ṛgyaditirditiś N;
ṛgyādītidaditiś G2; ṛgyāditiś G3; rudrāditiś M; ṛkāditiditi E
• diggatāḥ] N,E; diggataḥ G3; digataḥ G2; digdhatāḥ M

- 54.16 brahmā navapadāntasthaḥ syād āpaḥ syād īśakoṇataḥ
savitā cendrarudraś ca śeṣakoṇasthitāḥ pare
- 54.17 koṣṭhakāntaritanyāsād brahmapārśve tu samsthitāḥ
prāgdikto yāvad īśāntaṃ ṣaṭpadaḥ sa marīcakaḥ M2c p169
N f80v; G3 f89r
- 54.18 sāvītro dvipado jñeyo vivasvān ṣaṭpado mataḥ
tadvad indrajayo mitro dvipadaḥ ṣaṭpadaḥ sthitāḥ G2 f186v
- 54.19 rudradāso dvikoṣṭhasthaḥ ṣaṭpadaḥ pṛthivīdharāḥ
āpavatsaḥ sthitāḥ koṇe padadvayavimardakaḥ
- 54.20 evaṃ nyasya surān koṇāt koṇasūtraṃ nipātayet
ṛṭīyaṃ koṇakād anyat ṛṭīyaṃ koṣṭhakaṃ nyaset M1c p122

G = G2, G3 (and G3c) M = M1c and M2c Ω = N G M
G3 (and G3c) lack 18b-19c before koṇe.

16a brahmā] N,G,M; brahmaṃ E • nava] N,G,E; nava M • padāntasthaḥ] em.; padāntasthaṃ
E; padentasthāṃ G2; padentasthaṃ G3; padentasthaḥ M1c; padentasthaś M2c; padontaḥsyād N
16b āpaḥ syād īśakoṇataḥ] N; cā"paścaiśānakōṇagaḥ E; cāpascāpeśakoṇakaḥ G2;
cāpapālīśakoṇakaḥ G3; saścāpapāśagoṇakaḥ M1c; cāvapāśasagoṇakaḥ M2c
16c savitā cendra] N; savitendraś ca G,M,E 16d sthitāḥ] G3,E; sthitā N,G2,M
17a koṣṭhakāntarita] M,G,E; koṣṭhakāntaritā N • nyāsād] N,E; nyāsāt G3,M; ny[**]t G2
17b brahmapārśve tu] G,M,E; brahmaṇāpārśva N
• samsthitāḥ] N; samsthitā G3,M; samsthit[*] G2; samsthitāḥ E
17c prāgdikto yāvad] N; pratikoyāvad G2; pratikoyāvad G3,M; āpavatsas tad E
• īśāntaṃ] em.; īśāntaḥ N, M; īśānta G,E 17d padaḥ sa] N,M1c; padassa G,M2c; padastho E
• marīcakaḥ] E; marīyakaḥ N,G2,M; [****] G3 18a sāvītro dvipado jñeyo] em.;
sāvītrodvīṣadojñeyāḥ N; sāvītras syāt dvīpadago E; sāvītryasyādvīpadako G2;
sāvītryasyādvīpadiko G3; sāvītryāsyāddvīpadiko M1c; sāvītryasyātdvīpadiko M2c
18b vivasvān ṣaṭpado] N,M; vivasvān ṣaṭpade E; [*****]do G2
18c tadvad] N,M,E; [**] G2 • indra] N,G2,E; enda M • mitro] N,E; mrgyo G2,M
18d dvīpadaḥ] N; dvīpadaḥ G2,E; dvīpādaḥ M • ṣaṭpadaḥ] N,M1c; ṣaṭpada G2,M2c,E
19a koṣṭhasthaḥ] N; koṣṭhasthaś E; ko[**] G2; koṣṭhastadā M1c; koṣṭhastat M2c
19b padaḥ pṛthivīdharāḥ] N,G2; pādapṛthivīdharāṃ M; padastho dharādharāḥ E
19c āpavatsaḥ sthitāḥ] conj.; āpavaḥsamsthitāḥ N; athavā samsthitāḥ E; athavatsamsthitāḥ G2,M
19d vimardakaḥ] N; vimardhakaḥ M,G2; vimurddhyataḥ G3; atha 'ryataḥ E
20a koṇāt] N,G; koṇān M; koṇe E 20b sūtraṃ] N,G,M1c,E; sūtra M2c 20c ṛṭīyaṃ]
conj.; ṛṭīya] G,M,E; ṛṭīyā N • koṇakād] N; koṇakāl G,M,E • anyat] N,G2,M; ānyat G3,E
20d ṛṭīyaṃ] G,M,E; ṛṭīyā N • koṣṭhakaṃ] N,G3,M,E; ko[[ṇa]]ṣṭhakaṃ G2 • nyaset] G,M,E;
nyet N

- 54.21 tat sūtram ubhayoḥ paścāt pārśvayor brahmaṇaḥ kramāt
koṣṭhaṃ madhyasthitam neyaṃ caturdikṣu vyavasthitam
- 54.22 vaṃśās te catvāraḥ khyātāḥ koṇasūtram sirā matāḥ
evaṃ jñātvā tu saṃśleṣaṃ sūtrāṇaṃ marma tad bhavet
- 54.23 jñeyaṃ madhyagataṃ marma tac ca yatnena varjayet
kṛtvā tat ṣoḍaśāṃśaṃ tu tatraikaṃ marma tad bhavet
- 54.24 kṛtvā ṣoḍaśadhā sthānaṃ varjayet tat sadaiva tu
īśāne 'sya śiro vāstor bāhur madhyaṃ ca vahnigam
- 54.25 savitā hastasthitaś ca nairṛte caraṇadvayam
āpaḥ kaṅṭhapradeśaḥ syād āpavatso hr̥di sthitaḥ

G = G2, G3 (and G3c) M = M1c and M2c Ω = N G M

21a ubhayoḥ] G3,M,E; u[[pa]]bhayoḥ G2; ubhayo N 21b pārśvayor] N,M2c;
pārśvayoḥ G2,M1c,E; pārśvayo G3 • brahmaṇaḥ] G2,M,E; brāhmaṇaḥ N,G3
21c koṣṭhaṃ] M; koṣṭha N,G,E • neyaṃ] N,G,E; neyāt M1c; jñeyaṃ M2c
22a vaṃśās te catvāraḥ khyātāḥ] em.; paṃsāstecaturāḥkhyātāḥ N; khyātāṃ vaṃśās ca
catvāraḥ M1c,E; khyātāṃvaṃśāccacatvāraḥ G2; khyātāṃpaṃśāccacatvāraḥ M2c;
khyātāmaṃśāccacatvāraḥ G3 22b sūtram] G,E; sūtra N,M • śirā] G3,M; sirā G2;
sivā N; śiro E • matāḥ] N; matā G3,M; mataḥ G2; mataṃ E22c saṃśleṣaṃ] N; saṃśleṣa
G,M2c; saṃśleṣā M1c; saṃśleṣāt E 22d sūtrāṇaṃ] G2,N,M,E; sūtrāṇā G3 •
marma tad] N; mamataṃ G; amitaṃ M,E 23a marma] N; mahyaṃ G2; madhyaṃ
G3,M,E 23b tac ca] N,G,M2c,E; tajja M1c 23c tat] G,M,E; hyā N
23d tatraikaṃ marma] N; tatrīkamama G2; tattrikaṃmama M; tatrakarmaca G,E
• tad bhavet] N; tatpunaḥ G,M,E 24a ṣoḍaśadhā G,M,E; ṣoḍasakaṃ N
24b sadaiva] N,G,E; sadeva M 24c īśāne 'sya] G2,E,G3; īśānasya M; īśāṃnyasya N
• vāstor] G2,E; vāsto N,G3; vāste M 24d bāhur] G3; bāhu N,G2,M; bāhū E • madhyaṃ
ca] N,G,M1c; dhyamca M2c; dvau vāyu E • gam] N,M,G; gau E 25a savitā hastasthitaś
ca] conj.; kiraṇe pi savitā hasto 'syeti MY comm 4 f30r top; savitātasthitaśtasya N;
ahasthitaścasavitā G; ahaḥsthitaścasavitā M1c; ahāsthitaścasavitā M2c; aṃśayossavitā E
25b nairṛte] G,M; nairite N; nirṛtau E
25c āpaḥ kaṅṭha] em.; āpakaṅṭha N; ākhaṅḍala G,M; ākhaṅḍalaḥ E
• pradeśaḥ] N; pradeśā G,M; pradeśe E • syād] N,E; syāt G,M
25d āpavatso] N,E; āpasoyaṃ G2; tāpasoyaṃ G3,M2c; tāpaso'yaṃ M1c
• sthitaḥ] G,M,E; sthitā N

- 54.26 sa marīko dharākhyāś ca stanasthau tau sthitāv iha
brahmā nābhigataḥ proktaḥ sāvitraḥ kukṣigo mataḥ G2 f187r
- 54.27 indraś cendrajayo guhye vivasvān ūrugo mataḥ
mitro hy aparagas tadvad bhaved aṅgadvitīyakam M2c p170
- 54.28 purā hy utpātavad bhūtaṃ dṛṣṭvā devaiḥ subhīṣaṇam
grhītvā taiḥ samastais tu prakṣiptaṃ tad adhomukham
- 54.29 yathā yena grhītaṃ tu pūjanīyaṃ tathaiva tat
yad vāstu prathitaṃ cātra grhaprāsādakalpane
- 54.30 ekāśītipadaṃ khyātaṃ catuḥṣaṣṭipadaṃ śṛṇu
tat kṣetram aṣṭadhā kṛtvā nyased īśāditaḥ surān G3 f89v

G = G2, G3 (and G3c) M = M1c and M2c Ω = N G M

26a sa marīko] N, G3,M; samarīcako G2; marīcī E
 • dharākhyāś] N,G; dharākhyāś M; bhūdharākhyau E 26b stanasthau tau sthitāv
 iha] N; G2,M; stanasthautauviha G3; stanasthānasthitāv ubhau E
 26c brahmā nābhi] G3,M,E; brahm[*]nābhi G2; brāhmaṇābhi N
 • gataḥ] N,G,M; gato E • proktaḥ] N,G3,M; prokta G2; raudra E
 26d sāvitraḥ] N,M; sāvitra G2; savitraḥ G3; sāvitrau E • kukṣigo] N; kukṣigau E;
 kukṣiko G; kukṣito M • mataḥ] N,G,M; matau E 27a indraś cendra] G,M1c,E;
 indraścendṛ M2c; indramindra N • jayo] N,G3,M,E; jaye G2 27b vivasvān] N,G,E;
 vivasvā[-] M1c; vivasvā M2c • ūrugo mataḥ] conj.; ūrugo mataḥ N; rubhomataḥ G;
 ruhomataḥ M; ūrumadhyagaḥ E 27c hy aparagas] N; [*]yāparagas G2; nyāpāragas
 G3; nyāpagatas M; 'nyorugakas E • tadvad] N; tadvat G,M,E 27d bhaved] N;
 bhavaty G,M; praty E • aṅga] N,M,G3; aṅgaṃ E,G2 • dvitīyakam] N,M,G;
 devatātmakaṃ E 28a purā] N; parā G,M; para E • hy utpātavad] M; hyutpātavat G;
 nyutpatavad N; mutpātavad E 28b devaiḥ] N; bhītais E; hīnais G,M
 • su] N,G,E; sa M 28c taiḥ] em.; tais N,G3,M2c,E; tai G2; te M1c
 • samastais] N; samastās M1c; samantās M2c,G2; samantaḥ G3; samantāt E
 28d prakṣiptaṃ] G2,M,E; prakṣiptaṃ G3; prakṣipet N 29a tu] G,M; tat N; yat E
 29b tat] G3,M,E; t G2; saḥ N 29c yad] G,M,E; sa N
 • prathitaṃ] E; prathitas N; pratitaṃ G3,M1c; prakṛtaṃ M2c; pūjanaṃ G2
 29d kalpane] N,G2,E; kalpanam M,G3
 30a padaṃ khyātaṃ] G,M,E; padaḥkhyātaḥ N 30b catuḥ] N; catuṣ G,M,E
 30d īśāditaḥ] N; īśāditas M,E; īśādita[[t]]s G2; īśāditat G3 • surān] N,G,E; svarān M

54.31 ditīśaś cāntarikṣāgnimṛgaś ca pitṛsaṃjñakāḥ
pāpayakṣmā ca rogaś ca koṇārdhasthā divaukasāḥ

N f81r

54.32 parjanyaś ca jayantaś ca mahendro bhāskaraḥ kramāt
satyo bhr̥śaś ca pūrvāyāṃ pūṣā dakṣiṇataḥ sthitaḥ

54.33 vitatho gṛhamṛtyuś ca gandharvo bhr̥garāṇ mataḥ
dauvārikāḥ pratīcyāṃ tu sugrīvaḥ kusumadvjiaḥ

54.34 vārīśaś cāsuraś śoṣo nāgaś cottarataḥ sthitaḥ
mukhyo bhallāṭasomaś ca ṛgiś caivāditiḥ kramāt

M1c p123

54.35ab ete dvipadikā jñeyā madhye brahmā catuṣpadaḥ

G = G2, G3 (and G3c) M = M1c and M2c Ω = N G M

31a ditīśaś] conj.; digīśas N; dvitīyaṃ G2; dvitīyā G3,M; dvitīye E • cāntarikṣāgni] N; hyāntarikṣāgni E; hyāntarikṣāni M,G 31b mṛgaś ca] N,G3; mṛgaṃca G2,M; mṛgarāḍ E • pitṛ] N,M,E; papitṛ G • saṃjñakāḥ N,G2; saṃjñakam M,G3; saṃjñakāḥ E 31c yakṣmā ca] N; yakṣmaga G,M; yakṣmā 'nga E 31d koṇārdhasthā] N,E; koṇārdhastha M; koṇārdhāsva G • divaukasāḥ] G,M,E; divaukasāḥ N 31a jayantaś] G,M,E; jayantī N 32b bhāskaraḥ] N,M1c,E; bhāskara G; bhaskara M2c 32c satyo] N; tasyo G,M,E • bhr̥śaś] conj.; bhr̥gvas N; ddhṛtaś G,M1c; ddhṛtam E; ddhṛta M2c • pūrvāyāṃ] G,M,E; pūrvvāyā N 32d dakṣiṇataḥ] N,M; dakṣiṇatas E; dakṣiṇata G 33a vitatho] N,G; mitatho M; vithātā E • gṛhamṛtyuś ca] G,E; 33b gandharvo] M,G,E; gāndharvvo N • rāṇmataḥ] G,E; rāṭmataḥ N; rāṇataḥ M2c; rājataḥ M1c 33c dauvārikāḥ] E; dauvārika G3; dvauvārika N,M2c; dvāvārikāḥ M1c; dvavāka G2 • pratīcyāṃ tu] G,M,E; tathāprācyāṃ N 33d sugrīvaḥ] G,M,E; sugrīva N 34a vārīśaś cāsuraś]G,E; vārīśaścasuraś M; parivāṭasuraḥ N 34ab śoṣo nāgaś] conj.; śoṣorogaś G2; śoḍasanāgas N; śaināgaś G3; śona[– –]gaś M; caiva nāgaś E 34b cottarataḥ sthitaḥ] G2; cottarataḥsthitāḥ N; cottaratas sthitaḥ E; cottarasthitaḥ G3; cottataḥsthitāḥ M 34c mukhyo] N,G2,E; mukhya G3; mukhye M • bhallāṭasomaś ca] M2c; bhalvāṭasomaśca G; bhallāṭasomo ca E; bhallāṭasomeca M1c; bhallāṭakaḥsaumya N 34d ṛgiś] G; ṛk E; giriś N,M2c; girirugiś M1c • caivāditiḥ] N,M2c; caivāditaḥ G3,M1c; caivādigaḥ G2; cāditiditī E 35a dvipadikā] N; dvipadagā E; dvipādakā G3,M; [–]kā G2 • jñeyā] G,M,E; jñeyāḥ N 35b brahmā catuṣpadaḥ] G3,M,E; brahm[****]daḥ G2; brahmācatuṣpadā N

54.35cd tathāpaś cāpavatsaś ca sāvitraḥ savitā paraḥ

54.36 indraś cendrajayo rudro rudradāsaḥ kramāt sthitaḥ
koṇārdhasamsthitaḥ hy ete tripadaḥ sa marīcakaḥ

54.37 vivasvāṃś ca tathā mitro bhavet tadvad dharādharah
taccatuṣkoṇapārśvasthā devās cāṣṭau padasthitāḥ

M2c p171

54.38 pūrvavac ca sirā vaṃśān tathā marma prakalpayet
ayaṃ devālaye prokto dvitīyo mandire mataḥ

54.39 vāstusamkalpakāle tu yad aṅgaṃ sprśate grhī
vāstudehe 'pi tatraiva śalyoddhāraavidhir mataḥ

54.40ab śiraḥsparśād grheśasya hastiśalyaṃ narārdhataḥ

G = G2, G3 (and G3c) M = M1c and M2c Ω = N G M

35c tathāpaś] em.; tathā"paś E; tathāpo N; tadāpaś G,M • cāpavatsaś] G,M; cā"pavatsaś E; hyāpavatsas N 35d sāvitraḥ savitā] N; savitrasāvitrakau E; savitresavitaḥ G,M • paraḥ] N; param G,M,E 36a cendra] G,E; cendrā N; cendre M1c; cendro M2c • rudro] G3,M,E; rudraḥ N; rudrā G2 36b dāsaḥ] M,E; dāsa N,G 36c koṇārdhasamsthitaḥ] G,M,E; arddhakoṇagatā N 36d tripadaḥ sa] em.; tṛpadaḥsa N; tripadassa G,M; tripadastho E • marīcakaḥ] N,E; marīcaka[*] G2; marīcaka G3,M2c; marīcika M1c 37a vivasvāṃś] G,M,E; vivasvāṃ N 37b tadvad] N,G,M2c,E; tattad M1c • dharā] N,G,E; varā M 37c koṇa] N,G,M1c; keṇa M2c,E • sthā] N; stha G,M,E 37d devās cāṣṭau] G,M; devās cāṣṭa E; devāṣṭau N • padasthitāḥ] G,M,E; padakalpitaṃ N 38a ca sirā] N; casurā G3,M; ca surān E; sa[*] G2 • vaṃśān] E; vaṃśā N; vaṃśa G,M 38b marma] N; bhūma G,M; bhūmau E 38c ayaṃ] N,G,E; aya M • prokto] N,G,E; prokte M 38d dvitīyo] G2,E; dvitīye N,G3,M • mataḥ] G,M,E; matam N 39b aṅgaṃ] em.; aṅga N; aṃśaṃ G3,M,E; āsaṃ G2 39c dehe 'pi] M,E; dehopi G3; deheṃvi G2; devepi N • tatraiva] G,M,E; nirmmathyā N 39d śalyoddhāra] N,G,E; śalyodvāra M • vidhir] N,G,E; vidhaṃ M1c; viyat M2c • mataḥ] N,G,E; matam M 40a śiraḥ] M1c; śiras E; śira N,G,M2c • sparśād] N,G2,M1c,E; sparśāt G3,M2c 40ab grheśasyahasti] N; grheśasyaāsti G; grhetasyaāsti M2c; grhetasyāsti M1c; grheśasya hema E 40b śalyaṃ] N,E; śalya G,M2c; śalyā M1c

54.40cd hastadvaye mukhasparśāt kāṣṭhaṃ spr̥ṣṭe gale dhruvam

54.41 śṛīkhalā tu tribhir hastair upasparśe bhaved dhruvam
hastānām tu catuṣkeṇa paśuśalyaṃ bhavet khaga

54.42 khaṭvāpādaṃ karasparśāj jānumātrād adho bhavet
nalako bāhusaṃsparśād dhastatrayavikarṣitaḥ

G3 f90r

54.43 pādāmūlatalasparśāc carmānguṣṭhapramāṇataḥ
khaṭikānguṣṭhasaṃsparśād adho hastatrayeṇa tu

N f81v

G2 f188r

54.44 kaniṣṭhāṅgulisaṃsparśāt kāṃsyaṃ tatra karārdhataḥ
lohaṃ syāt kaṭakaṃ khyātaṃ kaṭisparśāt karadvaye

54.45 ūrusparśāt kāṣṭhas tatra dvādaśāṅgulato hy adhaḥ
jānusparśāc ca hastena nāpitopaskaro dhruvam

G = G2, G3 (and G3c) M = M1c and M2c Ω = N G M

N lacks 41ab. M2c2c lacks 42bc.

With 43c khaṭikānguṣṭha, compare DM 80.85cd: aṅguṣṭhake yadā kaṇḍū
khaṭikāśalyam ādiśet

40c dvaye] G,M,E; dvayor N 40d kāṣṭhaṃ] N,E; kāṣṭhā G,M • spr̥ṣṭe] N,G,M; pr̥ṣṭhe E
41a śṛīkhalā tu] G,M2c; śṛīṅgalātu M1c; asthiśalyaṃ E 41b upasparśe] E; upasparśo G2;
ukasparśo G3,M • bhaved dhruvam] M2c; bhavetdhruvam G2,E; bhavel]**] G2; bhavaddhruvam
M1c 41c hastānām] N,G2,M,E; [*]stānām G3 • catuṣkeṇa] N,G2,E; catuṣkoṇa G3,M
41d paśu] N,G; apa M; copa E • śalyaṃ] E; śalya N,G,M • bhavet] G,M,E; ḡhāt N
42a khaṭvā] N; khaṭga G2; khaḍga G3,M; khaḍgaṃ E • pādaṃ] em.; pāda N,G,M,E • kara] N;
para] G,M,E • sparśāj] N,G,E; sparśāt M 42b jānu] G,M1c,E; jāta N 42c nalako] N;
gaḷako G,M1c; gaṇḍako E • bāhusaṃsparśād] N,E; bāhusaṃsparśāt G2,M1c; [***]sparśād G3
42d dhasta] N,G,E; hasta M • traya] N; mātra] G,M,E • vikarṣitaḥ] N,G,M; vikarṣataḥ E
43a tala] N; daḷa G,M,E • sparśāc] N,G3,E; sparśāt G2,M 43c khaṭikānguṣṭha] conj.
Sanderson; khaṭikānguṣṭha N; peṭikānguṣṭha E; khaṭikāṅgula G,M • saṃsparśād] E; saṃsparśāt
N,G,M1c; saṃsparśā M2c 43d adho] E; tāśca N,M1c; āśca G,M2c
44a kaniṣṭhāṅguli] N; kaniṣṭhāṅguḷi E; kaniṣṭhāṅguṣṭha G,M • saṃsparśāt] N,G2,M,E;
saṃsparśādasya G3 44b kāṃsyaṃ] N,E; kāṃsya G2; kāṃsaṃ G3,M • tatra] N,G3,M; tattra
E; [**] G2 • karārdhataḥ] N,G,M2c,E; karāgrataḥ M1c 44c lohaṃ syāt] E; lohasyā G,M;
lohasya N • kaṭakaṃ] G,M,E; kaṇṭhakaḥ N • khyātaṃ] G,M,E; khyātaḥ N 44d sparśāt]
G3,M,E; sparśā G2; sparsā N • karadvaye] G,E; karadvayoḥ M; dvayekaraḥ N 45a kāṣṭhas]
conj.; karas N,G,M,E 45cd hastena nāpitopaskaro] em.; hastenanāpikopaskaro N;
hastenanatīdhopaskaraṃ G2; hastenanadhītopaskaraṃ G3,M; hastenāpy ayaś śalyaṃ bhavet E

54.46 gulphasparśād dhayapādaḥ sa vitastipramāṇataḥ
pādasparśād gajasyāsthi dvādaśāṅgulato dvija

54.47 evaṃ saṃkṣepataḥ proktaḥ śalyoddhārakramo mayā
evaṃ viśodhya tāṃ bhūmiṃ kāryaṃ vāstusurārcaṇam

M2c p172

54.48 īśānādikramāt pūjā kāryā pūrvam ghṛtākṣataiḥ
nīlotpalodakaṃ dadyāt patākāṃ pītavarṇikāṃ

M1c p124

54.49 ratnāni dhūmravaitānaṃ dadyāt taṃ maṇḍakān ghṛtam
māṃsāni śakuniṃ srucīṃ lājā homakramān madhu

54.50 māṃsodanaṃ punar gandhaṃ rasanā śakunodbhavā
tilā yavatilair bhaktā dantakāṣṭhaṃ ca yāvakaṃ

G = G2, G3 (and G3c) M = M1c and M2c Ω = N G M

with 46a dhayapādaḥ, compare PI 9.85d dhayapādaṃ

46a sparśād] N,G,M; sparśāt E 46ab dhayapādaḥ sa] em.; dhayaḥpādassa G3,M1c;
dhamahpādassa M2c; dhataḥpādassa G2; dharepādaḥsa N; trapuś śalyaṃ syād E
46b vitasti] N,G,E; vitahstri M1c; vitasstri M2c 46c pāda] G,M,E; pāyu N
• sparśād] N,M1c,E; sparśāt G,M2c • gajasyāsthi] E; gajasyātra] N,G; bhajasyātra M
46d dvādaśāṅgulato] N,E; dvādaśāṅgulate G,M • dvija] G3,E; dvijaḥ N,G2; dvijaḥ M
47a saṃkṣepataḥ] N,G3,M,E; saṃkṣobhataḥ G2
• proktaḥ] N,M; proktaś G3,E; proktaṃ G2 47b mayā] N,G3,M,E; marā G2
47c viśodhya] N,G2,M; viśoddhya G,E 48a kramāt] N,G,E; kramād M
48ab pūjā kāryā] N,E; bījakāryaṃ G,M 48b pūrvam] G,E; pūrva M; pūrvvā N
48d patākāṃ] N,G3; pātakāṃ G2; pākāṃ M; pādukāṃ E
• varṇikāṃ] N,G,M2c; varṇakāṃ E,M1c
49b maṇḍakān] N,G,M2c,E; mandhakāṃ M1c
• ghṛtam] M; ghṛtāṃ N,G,E 49c śakuniṃ] G,E; sakuni N; kṛnīṃ M
• srucīṃ] em.; sūcī N; sūci G,M,E 49d lājā] N,G; lāja M1c,E; balāja M2c
• kramān] N,G3,E; kramā G2,M • madhu G,M,E; madhuḥ N
50a māṃsodanaṃ] G,M; māṃsaudanaṃ E; māṃsodana N
50a gadhaṃ] em.; gandha N; dagdhaṃ M2c, E; ddagdhaṃ G; dugdhaṃ M1c
• rasanā] M, G,E; rajanā N 50b śakunodbhavā] E; śākunodbhavā M; sakunodbhavāḥ
N; śakuśotbhavā G2; āsanotbhavā G3 50c tilā] G,E; nīla N; tilo M • yava] G3,E;
yavā N; yāva G2,M • tilair G3,M,E; tidhair G2; tilā N • bhaktaṃ] G,M,E; bhaktā N
50d yāvakaṃ] N,E; yāvakaṃ M,G

54.51 kuśān padmaṃ surāṃ dadyād ghṛtānnaṃ ca yathākramāt
ghṛtāktān maṇḍakān dadyān nānā puṣpāṇi pūrikām

54.52 mudgānnaṃ kṣīraśālūkalopyaś cāpūpakā punaḥ
evam iṣṭvā kramād devān paścāt koṇasthitān yajet

54.53 payodadhīśakoṇe tu kuśavāriḡuḡodanam
etad āgneyakoṇe tu haridrāmiśram odanam

G3 f90v

54.54 etac ca nairṛte dadyāt pakvāpakvaṃ ca phalguṣam
vāyavye koṇagāḥ pūjyāḥ pūrve caiva tu laḡḡukam

54.55 raktaṃ malayajaṃ yāmye ghṛtānnaṃ vāruṇe punaḥ
phalguṣam māśakaṃ bhakṣyam uttare tat pradāpayet

N f82r

G = G2, G3 (and G3c) M = M1c and M2c Ω = N G M

- 51a kuśān] N,G,E; kuśāt M • padmaṃ] G,M,E; padma N
• surāṃ] N,G,M1c,E; surād M2c • dadyād] N,E; dadyāt G,M
51b ghṛtānnaṃ] em.; ghṛtānāṃ] N,G,M,E
51c ghṛtāktān] N,E,G,M1c; ghṛtāktam M2c • maṇḍakān] N,E,G; mandhakāṃ M
• dadyān] N,G,E; dadyāt M 51d nānā] M2c,E; nā[*] G2; nā G3,M1c; nāga N
• puṣpāṇi] N,G,M; puṣpādi E • pūrikām] conj.; pūrikā N; pūrvakam M,G,E
52a mudgānnaṃ] G3,M; mudgānna N,E; [***] G2 • kṣīra] G,M,E; kṣīri N; [**] G2
• śālūka] N; śālōka G3,M; [**ka] G2; śālyannair E 52b lopyaś cāpūpakā] conj.
Sanderson; lopyastāpūpakā N; lāvyastapūvakā G,M; balis tattroktavat E
52c evam iṣṭvā] G,M,E; evampūjya N 53a tu] G,M,E; ṣu N
53b kuśa] N,G,M1c,E; kaśa M2c
• guḡodanam] N; gulodanam M,G3; [**]danam G2; guḡaudanam E
53c āgneya] N,M,E; āgneśa G • tu] G,M,E; ṣu N
54a nairṛte] G2;M,E; nairṛtai G3; nairite N
54b pakvāpakvaṃ] N,G,E; pakvaṃpakvaṃ M
• phalguṣam] N,E; phaḡguṣam G2; pha[*]guṣam G3; phaḡgulam M
54c koṇagāḥ pūjyāḥ] conj. Sanderson; koṇakāḥpūjyāḥ G,M; koṇake pūjyāḥ E;
koṇamāpūjyā N
54d pūrve caiva tu] N; pūrvenaiva ca E; pūrvenaivasa G2; pūrvenaivaca G3,M
• laḡḡukam] E; laḡḡukām N; laḡḡuka G2,M; laḡḡukaḥ G3
55c māśakaṃ] G,M,E; māśajam N • bhakṣyam] G,M,E; bhaktam N

54.56 tilājyaṃ pañcagavyaṃ ca madhye dadyāt kuśākṣatam
evaṃ sampūjitā devāḥ śāntim āśu prakurvate

54.57 atha tilākṣatair bhakṣyaiḥ puṣpaiḥ sarvāṃs tu pūjayet
abhāvāt kuśapuspair vā pūjya prāsādam ārabhet

M2c p173

iti kiraṇākhye mahātantre catuṣpañcāśat paṭalaḥ

G = G2, G3 (and G3c) M = M1c and M2c Ω = N G M

56b madhye] G,M,E; madhyā N • kuśākṣatam] N; kuśākṣataiḥ E; kuśākṣataḥ G,M

56c sampūjitā] G,M,E; sampūjitāḥ N • devāḥ] N,M; devāś E; devā G

56d prakurvate] G,M,E; pravarttate N

57a atha] em.; athavā N,G3,M; athā G2; na cet E

• tilākṣatair] N,G3,M,E; tilākṣataiḥ G2 • bhakṣyaiḥ] G,M,E; bhaktaiḥ N

57b puṣpaiḥ] em.; puṣpais N,G,M,E • sarvāṃs] N,G2,M,E; sarvāṃgas G3

57c abhāvāt] N; athavā G,M,E

after 57 itikiraṇākhyemahātantre] N; śrīmatkīraṇākhyemahātantrecaryāpāde] G,M,E •
prāsādayogyasthānavidhiś E only • catuṣpañcāśat] N,M,G; caturviṃśatiḥ E